

Interreg

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Alpine Space

Forest EcoValue

REGIONAL CAPACITY BUILDING WORKSHOPS

D.3.2.1

RESPONSIBLE PARTNER: LGCA/PP7

Interreg Alpine Space Programme 21-27

Carbon neutral and resource sensitive Alpine region

SO 2.2: Promoting the transition to a circular and resource efficient economy

Forest EcoValue:

Supporting multiple forest ecosystem services through new circular/green/bio markets and value chains

Project ID: ASP0100005

List of the Forest EcoValue project partners

- PP1. Finpiemonte SpA – Regional financial and development agency / **Coordinator** [FINPIE]
- PP2. Lombardy Foundation for the Environment – Fondazione Lombardia per l’Ambiente [FLA]
- PP4. National Research Institute for Agriculture, Food and Environment – Institut National de Recherche pour l’Agriculture, l’Alimentation et l’Environnement [INRAE]
- PP5. Slovenia Forest Service – Zavod za Gozdove Slovenije [ZGS]
- PP6. Institute for Environmental Planning and Spatial Development GmbH & Co. KG – Institut für Umweltplanung und Raumentwicklung GmbH & Co. KG [Ifuplan]
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- PP8. University of Graz, Institute of Environmental Systems Sciences [UNIGRAZ]
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- PP10. The French National Forest Office – Office National des Forêts [ONF]
- PP11. Hozcluster Steiermark – Woodcluster Styria [HCS]

Document information

Work package:	WP3 - Transfer and take-up of the proposed solutions
WP lead:	PP7
Activity:	A.3.2
Authors:	Deliverable edited by the Forest EcoValue project partners under the supervision of WP leaders (PP7)
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Reviewers:	Reviewed by Susanna Longo (PP1)
Document version:	Final
Due date (month)	M36
Actual delivery date (month):	M40
Deliverable number:	D.3.2.1
Dissemination Level:	[x] PU: Public (available on the project website)
Type	Report

Disclaimer

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Glossary

CB Capacity Building

WP Work Package

FES Forest Ecosystem Services

ES Ecosystem Services

LL Living Lab

BM Business Model

PES Payments for Ecosystem Services

PP Project Partner

FINPIE Finpiemonte SpA – Regional financial and development agency

FLA Fondazione Lombardia per l'Ambiente

INRAE Institut National de Recherche pour l'Agriculture, l'Alimentation et l'Environnement

ZGS Zavod za Gozdove Slovenije – Slovenia Forest Service

Ifuplan Institut für Umweltplanung und Raumentwicklung GmbH & Co. KG

LGCA Lombardy Green Chemistry Association – Cluster Lombardo della Chimica Verde

UNIGRAZ University of Graz – Institute of Environmental Systems Sciences

CNPF Centre Régional de la Propriété Forestière - Regional Centre for Forest Property Auvergne-Rhône-Alpes

ONF Office National des Forêts

HCS Holzcluster Steiermark – Woodcluster Styria

ASFO Associazione Forestale (Forest Owners' Association)

PSR Programma di Sviluppo Rurale (Rural Development Programme)

GAL Gruppo di Azione Locale (Local Action Group)

SFS Slovenia Forest Service

SiDG Slovenski Državni Gozdovi – Slovenian State Forests

BSC Kranj Regional Development Agency of Gorenjska

DRAAF Direction Régionale de l'Alimentation, de l'Agriculture et de la Forêt

COFOR Association des Communes Forestières

SME Small and Medium-sized Enterprise

EU European Union

1. Introduction

This deliverable focuses on the **implementation of Capacity Building (CB) Workshops** across the partner regions. These workshops aim to equip stakeholders with the knowledge, tools, and skills necessary to understand, support, and engage in innovative forest-related business models and ecosystem service frameworks.

These activities, implemented under WP3, were designed to transfer the knowledge and solutions developed through the project’s pilot action in WP2. They were synergic with the piloting carried out in the network of five Living Labs and aimed to build awareness and strengthen stakeholders’ capacities at local, regional, and national levels.

Designed as interactive learning sessions, the CB workshops specifically target **local and regional public authorities, forest owners, SMEs, clusters, and other relevant actors**. The content is aligned with the methodologies and tools developed in WP1 and tested in WP2 Living Labs. Each workshop facilitates the transfer of knowledge on the valuation of FES, market frameworks, payment schemes, and governance models, promoting practical uptake and policy alignment.

Held in the different national contexts of the project partners (e.g. Austria, Italy, Germany, Slovenia, France), the workshops were tailored to regional needs and stakeholder profiles, while ensuring a transnationally coherent approach.

To ensure a distinct and targeted approach between the public events held within the Living Labs (D.2.1.2) and the Capacity Building Workshops, project partners engaged in a dedicated discussion to clarify the differing objectives, audiences, and formats of the two types of events. While Living Lab events primarily focused on co-design and participatory testing within the pilot territories, the CB workshops had a stronger emphasis on knowledge transfer, dissemination, validation of business models, and exploration of replicability and policy integration.

D.2.1.2. Intermediate and final public events

Target audience: Local/regional target groups in LLs

Purpose: provide updates to the local community and maintain transparency in order to foster the engagement of local target groups.

- ➔ **Intermediate event** keep local stakeholders informed to encourage the continued collaboration.
- ➔ **Final event** offer a comprehensive restitution of the results achieved and the long-term potential of the proposed solutions.

D3.2.1 Regional Capacity Building Workshops

Target audience: from LL territories to the wider region. Forest owners, businesses, public administrations, others.

Purpose: to promote the transferability of the project solutions and methodologies.

- ➔ **Build knowledge** for the adoption of the project solutions and methodologies
- ➔ **Focus on the ecological and economical aspects** to explain how they are addressed in the project

Possible format

Public Events

Key Objectives:

- **Intermediate Event:** Keep local stakeholders informed about the project's progress to encourage ongoing collaboration.
- **Final Event:** Provide a comprehensive presentation of the results achieved and highlight the long-term potential of proposed solutions.

Duration:

- ✓ **Intermediate Event:** 1-3 hours, focusing on concise updates and discussion.
- ✓ **Final Event:** at least half a day, allowing for detailed presentations, demonstrations, and discussions.

Capacity building workshop

Duration: Plan for a duration that accommodates brief presentations, interactive sessions, and Q&A. A typical format could be half a day or a full day.

Location: Choose an accessible venue for all participants. If possible, consider hybrid options to enable virtual participation.

Engaging the audience: Send targeted invitations with a well-defined preliminary agenda. Tailor presentations to address the needs and interests of each target group.

Possible structure (examples)

Intermediate Public Event /EXAMPLE

Session 1: Opening

Welcome address and introduction to the event's objectives. Brief overview of the project's progress and relevance to the community.

Session 2: Project Updates

Share updates on activities, milestones, etc.

Session 3: Stakeholder Interaction

- Facilitate a Q&A session or small group discussions to gather feedback.
- Encourage stakeholders to share their perspectives and suggestions.

Session 4: Closing

Capacity building workshop / EXAMPLE

Session 1: Introduction

- Brief overview of the workshop objectives and expected outcomes.
- Presentation of Forest EcoValue project and its ecological and economic solutions.

Session 2: Technical Deep Dive

- Ecological Aspects (TBD, presentation with practical example or success cases)
- Economic Aspects (TBD, presentation with practical example or success cases)

Session 3: Interactive Engagement / Hands-on Workshop:

- Engage participants in simulations or real-life scenarios using project tools.
- Examples: Training on sustainable forestry practices for forest owners, Interactive session where participants use project tools to evaluate land use scenarios, etc

Session 4: Discussion and Feedback (Q&A or session)

- Facilitate open dialogue to gather opinions and suggestions.
- Identify barriers to adoption and discuss potential solutions.

In order to prepare this deliverable, project partners collected and systematised information on the two regional CB workshops organised in each country, including:

- Agenda
- Number of participants
- Photos (or screenshots, if online)
- Target groups reached
- Press release
- Media appearance (if possible)

The following sections present a detailed description of the workshops implemented in each partner country.

2. Overview of Capacity Building Workshops

Between January 2025 and February 2026, **a total of ten Capacity Building workshops were organised** across the five partner countries within the framework of WP3. The events were delivered **in different formats** - in-person meetings, field visits, and online webinars - in order to maximise accessibility and ensure the involvement of both local stakeholders directly engaged in the Living Labs and broader national audiences.

The workshops addressed a range of thematic areas reflecting the diversity of the Living Labs and pilot actions, including:

- Forest Ecosystem Services (FES) valuation and integrated business model development;
- Carbon and biodiversity credits and innovative environmental finance instruments (e.g. reverse auctions);
- Wood biomass value chains and circular bioeconomy approaches;
- Tourism-related financing mechanisms and recreational ecosystem services;
- Governance frameworks and public-private cooperation models for sustainable forest management.

Overall, the workshops reached approximately 140 participants across the Alpine Space, including forest owners, SMEs, public authorities at different administrative levels, research institutions, sectoral agencies, and intermediary organisations. The following table provides a structured overview of the CB workshops implemented in each country.

Country	Date	Location	Format	Main Topics	Participants
Italy	8 May 2025	Ormea (CN)	In-person	Business model validation, ecosystem services evaluation, funding schemes, implementation roadmap	7
Italy	12 September 2025	Online	Webinar	Replicability and scalability of ES-based business models, policy integration	50
Slovenia	3 June 2025	Tržič	In-person	Wood biomass, municipal energy planning, stakeholder coordination	12
Slovenia	10 November 2025	Škofja Loka	In-person	Strategic forestry challenges, biomass integration, regional cooperation	12
France	16 January 2025	La Tour de Salvagny	In-person	Forest EcoValue methodology, FES valuation, PES instruments	10
France	11 June 2025	Annecy (Semnoz)	Field visit + workshop	Climate adaptation, forest management scenarios, ecosystem service trade-offs	36
Germany	30 January 2026	Online	Webinar	New forest value chains, carbon instruments, tourism-related financing	11

Germany	2 February 2026	Online	Webinar	Burial forests, governance frameworks, innovative financing mechanisms	12
Austria	26 June 2025	Zeltweg	In-person (not attended)	FES funding options, reverse auction model	0
Austria	30 July 2025	Graz	In-person	Reverse auctions, Living Lab results, governance and contractual frameworks	n.a.

3. Project overview

Forests of the Alpine Space play a key role in climate change mitigation and resilience, providing multiple ecosystem services (ES) and environmental and social benefits such as CO₂ absorption, air pollution reduction, biodiversity enhancement, and protection against natural hazards. However, they are threatened by abandonment, climate change, and territorial degradation, which progressively reduce natural resources and the provision of forest ES (FES). Maintenance costs of Alpine forests are high, and public funds and traditional wood value chains are insufficient to cover them. Economic valuation and payment schemes for FES are widely discussed but rarely successfully applied.

The Forest EcoValue project addresses this challenge by developing innovative, sustainable business models for forest management and maintenance, supporting new bio-based value chains and ES markets, and involving different sectors, public and private actors, and citizens. Restoring and maintaining healthy forests has been recognised as a source of value for the Alpine region, while also creating business opportunities and green jobs for Alpine communities.

The project focuses on a subset of FES from the following categories:

- **Provisioning** (e.g. biomass, raw materials, chemicals) with a specific focus on non-timber forest products, and on the production of woody biomass for energy, integrated into circular energy markets.
- **Regulating** (e.g. biodiversity, natural risk reduction, CO₂ absorption) concretely working on carbon and biodiversity credits, natural risk management through protective forests, and innovative environmental finance instruments such as green bonds and reverse auctions.
- **Cultural** (e.g. recreation, habitat experience, health) particularly enhancing recreational and tourism services and spiritual and cultural services.

These services have been explored and tested within Living Labs (LLs) across five countries, located in different Alpine territories and representing diverse ecological and socio-economic contexts:

- **Italy – Valle Tanaro, Piedmont:** The LL in Valle Tanaro explores innovative approaches to valorising chestnut groves, promoting non-timber forest products, developing carbon and biodiversity credits, and fostering experiential activities linked to forest and rural heritage.

- **France - Haute-Savoie:** Grand Annecy and Thonon LLs focus respectively on two aspects 1) recreational ecosystem services, enhancing the value of forests through the sale of experiences such as ecotourism, outdoor activities, and educational programmes 2) enhancing the value of water regulation services through a public-private partnership.
- **Slovenia – Karavanke Mountains, municipality Tržič:** The Slovenian LL addresses natural risk management with a focus on torrent control, advances solutions for wood biomass supply chains and promotes sustainable tourism and recreational use of forests.
- **Austria – Province of Styria:** The Styrian LL concentrates on biodiversity and habitat provision and carbon sequestration and storage through innovative financing mechanisms such as reverse auctions.
- **Germany – Tegernsee Valley, Upper Bavaria:** The German LL explores spiritual and cultural services, such as forest cemeteries with biodegradable urns, while also fostering habitat and biodiversity conservation through collaborative public–private partnerships.

Accordingly, the project is aiming to:

- Map and analyse the Alpine Space forests delivery capacity of FES;
- Identify and estimate the economic potential, define business models and FES market frameworks;
- Test the models/tools developed by the consortium in pilot LLs involving local players;
- Compare results at transnational level, identifying obstacles and facilitating factors;
- Analyse the need for innovative policies to foster forest maintenance, FES markets, and new value chains;
- Elaborate refined transferable tools/models and policy proposals to enable new markets and value chains and ensure the expected FES.

Throughout the project, a continuous participatory process is carried out within the Living Labs. Stakeholders' active involvement in these labs is essential for co-designing and testing models and tools, ensuring that the innovative approaches are rooted in local realities. In parallel, public events and capacity-building workshops have strengthened engagement, supported knowledge transfer, and provided regular updates on project activities. This participatory and long-term approach, tested across the five territories, is paving the way for refined, transferable tools and policy proposals that can unlock new markets and value chains while safeguarding the provision of ecosystem services in the Alpine Space.

Project duration: 42 months

4. Capacity building workshops in the different countries

4.1 Italy

Introduction

In Italy, two Capacity Building (CB) workshops were organised in 2025 to consolidate and disseminate the knowledge developed during transnational pilot action and the modelling and co-design phases of the Italian Living Lab.

The workshops represented a crucial step for sharing and discussing the progress and solutions emerging from the Pilot Action, also with an audience beyond the Living Lab participants.

They focused, among other aspects, on the integrated business model developed for the Tanaro Valley and on the exploration of potential funding, governance, and replication pathways.

The first workshop, held **in Ormea on 8 May 2025**, involved a group of key local actors — municipalities, forest consortia, ASFOs, cooperatives, and the Forestry School of Ormea. Its objective was to build technical and economic knowledge around the business model under development within the pilot action, supporting participants in understanding its assumptions, mechanisms, and potential applications in the local context.

The workshop adopted a technical yet accessible approach, aiming to make complex concepts understandable and to stimulate interaction and active exchange among a diverse audience with complementary backgrounds. The workshop also explored funding schemes for territorial projects, strengthening participants' capacity to identify financial opportunities — regional, national, and philanthropic — relevant to any future implementation.

The second workshop, conducted **online on 12 September 2025**, reached a broader audience, including professionals, researchers, and public authorities from many Italian Regions. It was designed as a capacity building and knowledge-sharing event, comparing the resolution resulting from the Italian Living Lab with those of other Alpine case studies, and stimulating a structured reflection on replicability, scalability, and integration into policy frameworks.

Across both CB workshops, several key messages emerged:

- The integrated business model as deriving from the Pilot Action was confirmed as technically sound and locally relevant, capable of generating measurable environmental, social, and economic impacts while maintaining alignment with regional forest policy instruments.
- Presenting the model and the solutions developed through the pilot action to **external actors with diverse and complementary expertise** during the CB workshops proved valuable for **collecting technical feedback and observations** on key aspects such as **economic metrics, governance mechanisms, and implementation feasibility**.
This exchange not only helped **disseminate the knowledge generated within the project**, but also **contributed to consolidating and strengthening the proposed solutions**, ensuring their **technical robustness and practical relevance**.

- Participants recognised the potential for public–private partnerships to sustain forest management activities, particularly those characterised by *negative economic return* (so-called *macchiatico negativo*) but high ecological value.
- Participants highlighted the need to broaden the scale of implementation, including more productive forest areas to improve economic balance and enhance credit generation efficiency.
- The workshop confirmed the transferability of the Valle Tanaro approach to other Alpine and Apennine territories, reinforcing the role of Living Labs as territorial incubators for FES-oriented innovation.

In summary, the two CB workshops marked the transition from the design and modelling phase to the strategic consolidation phase of the Living Lab, strengthening both local ownership and the visibility of the project outcomes beyond the local dimension.

Workshop 1 – Technical Validation and Co-Design Session

Date: 8 May 2025

Location: Ormea (CN), Italy

Format: In-person meeting

Duration: Approx. 3 hours

Objectives and Rationale

The first Capacity Building workshop of May 2025 was organised in synergy with the participatory process of the Valle Tanaro Living Lab.

The meeting was held in a small and operational format, involving the key stakeholders most actively engaged in the Living Lab, to ensure a focused discussion. Its objective was to provide a focus on some technical aspects of the integrated business model developed for the area, together with the economic metrics derived from the regional feasibility assessment. It also included a practical exercise and co-design session to define the implementation steps.

The workshop also aimed to:

- Facilitate dialogue between local practitioners and institutional representatives on how to integrate the model into existing planning and funding frameworks;
- Build knowledge on possible funding opportunities through regional, national, and EU programmes (e.g. Rural Development Funds, LIFE, and banking foundations);
- Establish the basis for a shared roadmap for the short-term continuation of Living Lab activities, through a practical co-design exercise.

Participants and Stakeholder Groups

The workshop gathered around 10 key stakeholders, representing the main categories of actors within the Valle Tanaro ecosystem:

Type of stakeholder	Stakeholders contacted for the workshop	Stakeholders participating in the workshop
National public authority (TG 1 and 2):		
Regional public authority (TG 3 and 4):	1	1 (Finpiemonte)
Local public authority (TG 5):	1	1 (Comune Ormea)
Enterprise, except SME (TG 6 and 7):	0	0
SMEs (TG 8 and 9):	2	2 (Consorzio Forestale, Coop. Volpe e il Mirtillo)
Business support organization (TG 10):	0	0
Sectoral agency (TG 11):	0	0
Interest groups including NGOs (TG 12-14):	1	1 (ASFO Pamparà)
General public (TG 13):		
Higher education, research org. (TG 17):		
International organization, EEIG (TG 18 – 19):		
Others (TG 16):	1	1 (Scuola Forestale)
TOTAL number of Stakeholders (sum):	7	7

This multi-actor composition ensured the representation of both operational forest managers and decision-makers, enabling a realistic assessment of the business model’s feasibility and governance requirements.

Agenda of the workshop

- Welcome and introduction – Context and objectives of the workshop.
- Presentation of the final Business Model and validation exercise
 - Training session on ecosystem services evaluation and business model construction.
 - Key metrics and assumptions.
 - Collective validation through a structured feedback session.
- Brainstorming on implementation roadmap
 - Identification of enabling conditions and potential funding sources.

Workshop Activities and Methodology

The workshop followed a hands-on and learning by doing approach, combining short technical presentations with facilitated group discussions.

- Business Model Validation: Participants analysed the model’s structure, revenue streams, and cost assumptions through visual tools such as flow diagrams and cash-flow projections. Stakeholders provided feedback on feasibility and scalability, focusing on management costs, productivity, and potential integration with initiatives like *Green Communities* and *Rural Development Programmes*.
- Scenario Reflection: The group reviewed economic simulations from the feasibility assessment, comparing scenarios with different co-financing levels (0%, 20%, 50%, 85%). Discussions identified

which options were most viable under local conditions and the level of public or private support required for profitable ecosystem-based forest management.

- Roadmap Co-Design: A final collective brainstorming session defined practical next steps, priority actions, and possible funding instruments. Key proposals included the role of community cooperatives and ASFOs as intermediaries between landowners and funding bodies, and exploring opportunities through banking foundation calls and regional pilot schemes supporting nature-based solutions and rural development.

Key Outcomes

- Knowledge transfer and capacity building: the involved stakeholders have been successfully trained on the basis of ecosystem services evaluation, and on business model canva development and validation.
- Validation achieved: The group confirmed the technical and economic soundness of the proposed model and its consistency with local conditions.
- Refinement of economic metrics: Stakeholders highlighted some mistakes in the estimation of cost and revenues metrics of some products (in particular regarding to chestnut production and orchard maintenance).
- Funding perspectives identified: Several active calls and funding lines were mapped, including PSR (Rural Development Programme) measures on silvo-climatic payments and biodiversity, LIFE sub-programmes, and local foundation grants.
- Governance and cooperation priorities: Participants agreed on the potential to strengthen joint management structures (ASFOs, consortia) and to formalise collaboration through local pacts or forest agreements.
- Follow-up actions defined: The Living Lab coordination team committed to elaborating a preliminary implementation roadmap based on the inputs gathered and to circulate it among participants for final remarks.

Workshop 2 – Capacity Building and Knowledge Sharing Webinar

Date: 12 September 2025

Location and date: Online (Microsoft Teams platform),

Format: Webinar with interactive session

Duration: Approx. 2 hours

Objectives and Rationale

The second Capacity Building event was a national-level webinar designed to share knowledge and disseminate the results of the Italian Living Lab *Valle Tanaro* within the wider Alpine partnership.

Unlike the first, more local and operational workshop, this session targeted a broader Italian audience of

professionals, researchers, and public officers in forestry, spatial planning, and environmental policy. Its main objectives were to:

- Present the *Forest EcoValue* methodological framework and key outcomes across the Living Labs;
- Showcase the integrated business model and roadmap developed for the *Valle Tanaro* pilot area;
- Encourage reflection on the model’s replicability, scalability, and policy integration across Italian regions;
- Strengthen stakeholder capacity on ecosystem-service-based business models and funding opportunities for sustainable forest management.

Participants and Stakeholder Groups

The webinar attracted approximately **50 participants** from various Italian regions, representing a wide spectrum of institutional and professional backgrounds:

- **Public authorities:** regional departments for environment and forestry, mountain unions, and technical staff of municipalities.
- **Professional and research community:** forestry consultants, academics, and researchers from universities and applied research institutes.
- **Associative and private sector representatives:** members of forest consortia, ASFOS, cooperatives, and NGOs engaged in forest and landscape management.
- **Project partners and observers:** representatives of Finpiemonte (lead partner), FLA and Walden srl.

Type of stakeholder	Stakeholders contacted for the workshop	Stakeholders participating in the workshop
National public authority (TG 1 and 2):		
Regional public authority (TG 3 and 4):		12
Local public authority (TG 5):	23	8
Enterprise, except SME (TG 6 and 7):	6	
SMEs (TG 8 and 9):	3	8
Business support organization (TG 10):	9	3
Sectoral agency (TG 11):		
Interest groups including NGOs (TG 12-14):	19	6
General public (TG 13):	7	
Higher education, research org. (TG 17):	7	13
International organization, EEIG (TG 18 – 19):		
Others (TG 16):		
TOTAL number of Stakeholders (sum):	74	50

This composition allowed for a diverse exchange between technical experts, policy practitioners, and territorial actors, promoting the diffusion of knowledge produced within the Forest EcoValue partnership.

Agenda of the workshop

- 11:00 – Introduction to the Forest EcoValue project
Overview of objectives, partnership, and transnational methodology.
- 11:20 – Presentation of the modelling activities and Living Lab results
Comparative overview of the business models developed in the Alpine Living Labs.
- 11:40 – Focus on the Italian Living Lab – Valle Tanaro
Detailed presentation of the business model, key metrics, and roadmap.
- 12:00 – Interactive workshop and discussion
Participants invited to comment on:
 - Strengths and weaknesses of the proposed model.
 - Conditions for replicability and scaling in other Italian regions.
 - Synergies with existing programmes and ongoing projects.
- 12:30 – Final debate and conclusions

Workshop Activities and Methodology

The event followed a two-part structure, combining informative presentations and participatory reflection:

- Presentation and benchmarking: The first part provided an overview of the Forest EcoValue transnational framework, presenting the various modelling exercises carried out across the partner regions (Austria, Germany, Slovenia, France, and Italy).
- In-depth focus on the Italian Living Lab: The integrated business model developed for the Valle Tanaro was presented, including quantitative data on forest interventions, product outputs, carbon and biodiversity credits, and social impacts.
Particular attention was given to the economic assumptions behind the model, its cost structure, and the price sensitivity of carbon credits under different funding scenarios.
- Interactive reflection: Following the presentations, participants joined an open discussion facilitated through a set of guiding questions.
Contributions were collected directly in a shared online document, allowing for immediate synthesis of key points. The use of AI was involved for a quick review of participants' contributions, extracting the main themes and reflections pointed out by participants.
The debate addressed:
 - The replicability of the model in other Italian mountain areas with similar ecological and socio-economic features.
 - Potential funding schemes and governance mechanisms to ensure continuity after the project's end.
 - The role of regional and national policies in supporting ecosystem-service-based forestry.

Key Outcomes

- Validation of the Business Model: Participants confirmed the technical robustness and policy alignment of the *Valle Tanaro* model, recognising its balanced integration of ecological, social, and economic components.

- Participatory and Integrated Vision: The inclusive, bottom-up approach—linking public institutions, private actors, and local associations—was appreciated for fostering trust and collaboration.
- Contextualisation and Transferability: The model’s territorial grounding was identified as its main strength, while its methodology was deemed adaptable to other Alpine and Apennine regions with appropriate local adjustments.
- Constraints Identified: Challenges included land fragmentation, high transaction costs, dependence on external incentives, and the need for stronger institutional anchoring.
- Improvement Proposals: Suggested actions involved reinforcing landowner associations (ASFOS), simplifying certification and PES systems, broadening funding through public–private mechanisms, and enhancing monitoring of long-term impacts.
- Funding Tools: Participants cited existing instruments (Rural Development Programmes, Green Communities, Smart Villages, GAL, banking foundations, *Filiera Futura*) and potential new measures, such as national incentives for forest planning and integrating carbon and biodiversity credits into management tools.
- Roles of Organisations: Universities and research centres were identified for technical support; ASFOS, cooperatives, and municipalities for territorial animation; and local authorities for project development and fundraising.
- Overall Feedback: The workshop received highly positive evaluations for its clarity, interactivity, and use of collaborative digital tools. Participants valued the balanced mix of technical input and open dialogue, suggesting the format as a model for future national and regional sessions.

Photos or screenshots

The screenshot shows a Microsoft Teams meeting interface. The main slide is titled "Workshop sui servizi ecosistemici forestali" (Workshop on forest ecosystem services). It features a background image of a forest and mountains. The text on the slide includes: "Sostenere i servizi ecosistemici delle foreste attraverso mercati circolari/verdi/bio-based e lo sviluppo di nuove catene del valore" (Support forest ecosystem services through circular/green/bio-based markets and the development of new value chains). Below this, it says "Workshop di capacity building Online, 12 Settembre 2025". The slide also includes logos for "Forest EcoValue" and "Co-funded by the European Union". A small pop-up window in the top right of the slide area says "Registrazione e trascrizione" (Recording and transcription) and "Avviata automaticamente in base alle impostazioni dell'organizzatore della riunione." (Automatically started based on the meeting organizer's settings). The Teams interface shows 28 participants, a "Termina evento" (End meeting) button, and a "Abbandona" (Leave) button. The browser address bar shows the URL: "https://teams.microsoft.com/v2/?meetingjoin=true#/meetup-join/19:meeting_ZW...".

The screenshot shows a Microsoft Teams meeting interface. The main slide is titled "Il Living Lab in Valle Tanaro" (The Living Lab in Valle Tanaro). It features a map of the Valle Tanaro region in Italy, with several locations marked. The text on the slide includes: "Un'area pilota in cui venissero rappresentate le opportunità e le risorse del territorio, dove poter sviluppare, testare e validare nuove idee e soluzioni." (A pilot area in which the opportunities and resources of the territory would be represented, where it would be possible to develop, test and validate new ideas and solutions). Below this, it says "Uno spazio per interagire, coinvolgendo tutte le parti interessate e permettendo a tutti di avere un ruolo attivo nel processo di innovazione e di trasformazione." (A space for interaction, involving all stakeholders and allowing everyone to have an active role in the innovation and transformation process). At the bottom, it says "Un processo partecipativo coordinato e facilitato, a cui tutti potessero contribuire per generare valore e trovare soluzioni a beneficio della comunità." (A coordinated and facilitated participatory process, to which everyone could contribute to generate value and find solutions for the benefit of the community). The slide also includes logos for "interreg Alpine Space" and "Forest EcoValue". The Teams interface shows 26 participants, a "Termina evento" (End meeting) button, and a "Abbandona" (Leave) button. The browser address bar shows the URL: "https://teams.microsoft.com/v2/?meetingjoin=true#/meetup-join/19:meeting_ZW...".

Press release and media appearances

LinkedIn post

Press release: <https://www.finpiemonte.it/news/workshop-online-dedicato-alla-valorizzazione-dei-servizi-ecosistemici-forestali>

4.2 Slovenia

Introduction

As part of the *Forest EcoValue* project, SFS has planned and implemented capacity building activities aimed at strengthening local knowledge and cooperation in the field of sustainable forest management and the use of wood biomass.

The first workshop was organised in Tržič in June 2025 and focused on promoting the use of wood biomass at the municipal level. A second workshop was held in November 2025 within the *Rural Development Committee Meeting of the Gorenjska Region* at SORA Development Agency, addressing modern challenges and strategic directions in forestry.

Through these initiatives, the aim is to bring together municipalities, forest owners, companies, and public agencies, fostering dialogue and collaboration for a more efficient and sustainable use of local forest resources.

Workshop 1 - “Use of Wood Biomass in the Municipality of Tržič”

Date: 3 June 2025, 13:00–16:00

Location: Inkubator Tržič, Tržič, Slovenia

Organiser: Slovenia Forest Service

Objective

The main goal of this capacity building workshop was to promote the use of biomass in the municipality of Tržič, to connect relevant stakeholders, enhance their knowledge, and present the Forest EcoValue project and its activities.

Agenda of the workshop:

- Arrival of participants and registration
- Introductory greetings by the organiser (Aleš Poljanec, Director of the Slovenia Forest Service for Professional Affairs)
- Presentation of the municipality’s work in the field of woody biomass (Peter Miklič, Mayor of the Municipality of Tržič)
- Presentation of the Forest EcoValue project and the use of woody biomass in the municipality (Živa Bončina, Slovenia Forest Service):
 - Legal frameworks and incentives
 - Potentials and demand for the use of wood biomass
 - Results of a survey on the use of wood biomass among major forest owners
- Example of good practice in the use of wood biomass – Municipality of Kočevje (Marin Radovčič, Komunala Kočevje):
 - Establishment of a district heating system using wood biomass in Kočevje
 - Organisation of biomass supply and purchase
- Workshop session: “How to increase wood biomass use in the municipality of Tržič” – presentation of group results
- Open discussion

Photos or screenshots:

Participants and Stakeholder Groups

Participants were invited via post, email, and phone, sometimes we called after sending an invitation. The organisers maintained direct contact with key stakeholders established during project activities. Invitations were extended to major forest owners (n=50), biomass-related companies, the Regional Development Agency of Gorenjska (BSC Kranj), the Local Energy Agency of Gorenjska, the Biomass Association of Slovenia (project observer), the Forest Owner Association of Gorenjska, Komunala Kočevje (municipal utility company responsible for biomass supply), and several departments of the Slovenia Forest Service.

Type of stakeholder	Stakeholders participating in the workshop
National public authority (TG 1 and 2):	Slovenia Forest Service – project FEV, local and regional units: 6
Regional public authority (TG 3 and 4):	
Local public authority (TG 5):	utility company, part of municipality Kočevje, responsible for biomass (Komunala Kočevje), Municipality Tržič, different departments: 3
Enterprise, except SME (TG 6 and 7):	Companies on the field of biomass Gajles d.o.o., Slovenian State Forests SiDG (company that managed state forests): 3
SMEs (TG 8 and 9):	

Business support organization (TG 10):	
Sectoral agency (TG 11):	
Interest groups including NGOs (TG 12-14):	
General public (TG 13):	
Higher education, research org. (TG 17):	
International organization, EEIG (TG 18 – 19):	
Others (TG 16):	
TOTAL number of Stakeholders (sum):	12

The workshop successfully reached important target groups, including representatives from different departments of the Slovenia Forest Service, municipal authorities (including the mayor), and companies such as Slovenian State Forests (SiDG) and the local firm Gajles. The involvement of the municipality was particularly valuable, as it plays a crucial role in developing spatial and energy plans and is often the key actor in establishing district heating systems.

Press release and media appearances if present: /

Workshop 2 - “Modern Challenges and Strategic Directions in Forestry”

Event: Rural Development Committee Meeting of the Gorenjska Region

Date: 10 November 2025, 12:30–15:30

Location: Škofja Loka, Slovenia

Organiser: Development Agency SORA, with Forest EcoValue contributing one dedicated session.

The second capacity building workshop was organised as part of the Rural Development Committee Meeting of the Gorenjska Region. It was focused on strategic challenges and opportunities in forestry, including sustainable forest management, the role of municipalities in forest planning, and the integration of biomass into local energy systems. In our session Forest EcoValue project and our work in the municipality of Tržič was presented.

The event gathered regional and local stakeholders, policy makers, and forestry experts, providing a platform to discuss practical approaches and policy frameworks supporting the objectives of the Forest EcoValue project.

Participants and Stakeholder Groups

The workshop targeted local authorities, forest owner associations, regional development agencies, and companies active in forest-based value chains.

Type of stakeholder	Stakeholders participating in the workshop
National public authority (TG 1 and 2):	Slovenia Forest Service, Triglav National Park: 7
Regional public authority (TG 3 and 4):	
Local public authority (TG 5):	municipalities of Tržič, Bled, Kranj, Škofja Loka, Železniki: 5
Enterprise, except SME (TG 6 and 7):	
SMEs (TG 8 and 9):	
Business support organization (TG 10):	development agencies BSC Kranj, LAS loškega pogorja, RAGOR, SORA: 6
Sectoral agency (TG 11):	Chamber of Agriculture and Forestry: 1
Interest groups including NGOs (TG 12-14):	Cultural club Tabor: 1

General public (TG 13):	
Higher education, research org. (TG 17):	Biotechnical center Naklo: 1
International organization, EEIG (TG 18 – 19):	
Others (TG 16):	
TOTAL number of Stakeholders (sum):	12

Photos or screenshots:

Press release and media appearances if present: /

4.3 France

Introduction

Within the Forest EcoValue project, the French Living Lab, coordinated by the Office National des Forêts (ONF), organised two capacity building (CB) workshops aimed at strengthening collaboration among forest managers, local authorities, and stakeholders in the Auvergne–Rhône-Alpes region. The first workshop took place on **16 January 2025** in La Tour de Salvagny and focused on introducing the Forest EcoValue approach, its methodology, and its potential to enhance the valuation and integration of forest ecosystem services (FES) into local management frameworks. The second workshop was held on **11 June 2025** in Semnoz, Annecy, combining a technical field tour with an interactive working session. It aimed to deepen discussions among stakeholders on sustainable forest management practices, climate change impacts, and trade-offs between different forest uses.

Both events gathered representatives from public authorities, ONF, COFOR, regional agencies, and other key stakeholders. They provided a platform for dialogue, awareness-raising, and exchange of technical solutions.

Key outcomes

- Strengthening understanding of the *Forest EcoValue* methodology and Living Lab participatory approach;
- Identification of technical and financial levers to promote FES at regional and municipal levels;
- Recognition of the need for a clearer institutional framework to support the promotion and remuneration of ecosystem services.

Workshop 1 – “Understanding the Challenges and Needs for Promoting Forest Ecosystem Services”

Date: 16 January 2025, 08:30–13:30

Location: 18 av. Monts d’Or, 69890 La Tour de Salvagny

Organiser: Office National des Forêts (ONF)

Objective

To introduce the Forest EcoValue project, discuss local challenges related to forest management, and explore tools to enhance the understanding and valuation of forest ecosystem services among practitioners and local decision-makers.

Agenda of the workshop

- Presentation of the Forest EcoValue project: context, methodology, and objectives (Martin Grau, ONF)
- Presentation of the Living Lab approach and participatory process, with a focus on the Great Annecy case study (ONF)
- Interactive workshop using the Fresco of Forest Ecosystem Services animation tool to identify challenges and needs for promoting FES
- Discussion among stakeholders and Q&A session (COFOR)

Key topics discussed

Stakeholders discussed the complexity of forest management in mixed public–private landscapes, high operational costs, and fluctuating wood prices. The Forest EcoValue framework was presented as a way to evaluate FES using biophysical and economic indicators, as well as to explore regional financial mechanisms such as payments for ecosystem services.

The example of the Moise ASL scheme, which compensates forest owners for protecting water sources, was also discussed as a replicable model.

Main outcomes

Participants agreed on the value of using tools such as the Fresco to train ONF staff and raise awareness among regional stakeholders. The workshop confirmed the potential for replicating Living Lab approaches in other French regions and identified the use of the tourist tax to maintain recreational forest services as an innovative funding model.

Photos or screenshots:

Photos of the animation tool : the fresco of forest ecosystem services

Participants and Stakeholder Groups

10 participants, including representatives from ONF (regional and departmental directorates), COFOR (association of forest municipalities), and local elected officials. Key stakeholders included ONF managers and regional forest authorities actively engaged in FEV implementation.

Workshop 2 – “Balancing Forest Uses and Ecosystem Services in the Face of Climate Challenges”

Date: 11 June 2025, 08:30–17:30

Location: Semnoz, 74000 Annecy

Organiser: Office National des Forêts (ONF)

Objective

To explore practical approaches to sustainable forest management in the context of climate change and to identify local strategies for balancing timber production, biodiversity, and recreational services.

Agenda of the workshop

- Technical field tour with ONF forest managers illustrating forest management actions (logging, recreational use, adaptation to climate impacts)
- Presentation of the Forest EcoValue project: context, methodology, and objectives (Frédérique Zelmire, ONF)
- Overview of regional Living Labs and participatory processes (ONF)
- Stakeholder workshop: prioritisation exercise on forest management scenarios and ecosystem service outcomes
- Discussion and synthesis of results

Key topics discussed

The field visit provided a basis for discussing sanitary fellings related to bark beetle attacks, the management of dying spruce stands, and the need to improve communication with the public regarding access restrictions during logging operations.

During the participatory exercise, stakeholders compared three forest management scenarios (light, moderate, intensive). The moderate approach - combining targeted interventions while maintaining forest cover - was identified as the most balanced option to ensure both forest resilience and service provision.

Main outcomes

- Validation of the Forest EcoValue approach as a useful framework for awareness-raising among technicians, elected officials, and local communities;
- Agreement on the importance of establishing a structured framework for the promotion of ecosystem services;
- Reinforced collaboration between ONF, COFOR, and regional authorities to disseminate replicable practices.

Photos or screenshots:

Field trip in Semnoz public forest

Presentation of Forest Eco Value project and Living Lab

Workshop about forest ecosystem services

Participants and Stakeholder Groups

The event brought together a diverse group of participants representing regional and local public authorities, ONF at national, regional, and local levels, COFOR, SMEs, NGOs, and research institutions. Attendance reflected strong engagement across the forestry and environmental governance landscape, with key stakeholders including ONF field teams, COFOR representatives, state forestry officers from DRAAF, and elected officials from the Greater Annecy area.

In total, 36 participants took part in the meeting: 4 from ONF, 6 from COFOR, 6 from NGOs, 3 from SMEs, and 1 from a forestry school, along with 11 key stakeholders, 2 representatives from DRAAF, and 3 from the Greater Annecy authorities. This broad and well-balanced representation ensured a comprehensive exchange of perspectives and reinforced the collaborative approach underpinning the project's activities.

Press release and media appearances, if present: /

4.4 Germany

Introduction

In Germany, **two Capacity Building workshops** were organised in **January and February 2026**. Both events were conducted online and were strictly by invitation only. They aimed to inform participants about the project, present innovative business models developed within the Living Lab network, and foster dialogue on new value chains for forests.

The workshops were organised by the FEV project partner **ifuplan** and focused on strengthening exchange among forest owners, foresters, public authorities, and relevant stakeholders, particularly in the Bavarian Alpine region.

While the first workshop introduced **selected business models** and stimulated initial reflections on their potential and challenges, the second workshop **deepened the discussion, with particular attention to enabling framework conditions and governance aspects**.

Workshop 1 - "New Value Chains for Forests 1"

Date: 30 January 2026, 13:30–16:30

Location: Online (Microsoft Teams)

Organiser: ifuplan

The workshop (in German "Neue Wertschöpfungsketten für Wald 1") aimed to inform participants about the Forest EcoValue project, present innovative business models, and foster dialogue on new value chains in forestry. Participation was strictly by invitation only.

The workshop organized by ifuplan was moderated by Anna Schopf, supported by Franka Beyer. Presentations were delivered by Thomas Dichtl, Stefan Marzelli and Andrea Emmer.

Objective

The primary objectives of Capacity Building Workshop 1 were to:

- Provide comprehensive information about the Forest EcoValue project and its results;
- Present selected business models from the Living Lab network and other good practice examples;
- Provide participants with ideas for new value chains in forestry;
- Identify the potential and challenges associated with new business ideas;
- Formulate recommended actions for policymakers and relevant stakeholders;
- Facilitate dialogue between forest owners, foresters, and local stakeholders.

Agenda of the workshop

- 13:30 – Welcome and introduction
- 13:45 – Presentation of the Project Forest EcoValue
- 14:00 – Presentation of selected business models followed by questions
- 15:00 – Break
- 15:10 – Discussion on development opportunities, obstacles and possible solutions for new business models
- 16:15 – Outlook and project completion
- 16:30 – End of the workshop

Key topics discussed

The workshop featured presentations on the following business models:

- Reverse Auction (LL Austria);
- Burial Forest (LL Germany);
- Integrated value chains and ecosystem services in Piedmont (LL Italy);
- Tourism Tax (LL France)

Public funding possibilities were also introduced, including payments for CO₂ certificates and funding schemes for reforestation measures linked to drinking water forests.

The Think-Pair-Share methodology was applied to guide bilateral exchanges in breakout rooms. Participants engaged in a structured exchange on the business models presented, reflecting on which approaches they considered particularly promising and explaining the reasons behind their assessments. The discussion also addressed the main challenges anticipated in the practical implementation of these models, including regulatory, financial, and organisational aspects. Furthermore, participants explored the framework conditions and support mechanisms that would be necessary to enable successful implementation. The insights and key points emerging from the discussions were subsequently consolidated and documented collectively on a shared Miro board.

Main outcomes

Participants showed particular interest in payments for CO₂ certificates and tourism tax for recreation services.

Carbon-based instruments were perceived as promising due to growing regional demand. However, potential competition between CO₂ certification revenues and public funding schemes was identified, particularly regarding financial overlaps. Concerns were also raised about regulatory requirements potentially constraining forest management and timber use. Pooling models were proposed as a solution to improve economic viability and administrative efficiency.

Tourism-related business models were considered particularly relevant in highly touristic regions. Opportunities include improved cooperation between forestry and tourism, financial compensation for forest owners, and strengthened forest owner associations through pooling mechanisms. Challenges include dependence on municipal decision-making and possible stakeholder resistance to tourism-based charges.

Non-timber forest products were recognised as socially relevant, generating high public engagement and raising awareness. Guided forest tours for fruit and mushroom collection were highlighted as illustrative examples.

The discussion emphasised the importance of maintaining multifunctional forestry. New value chains should complement sustainable timber production. Concepts such as sponge landscapes and biodiversity-oriented certification schemes were discussed as promising additions aligned with public funding frameworks.

Participants and Stakeholder Groups

Invitations were extended to 52 organisations across nine target groups. A total of 16 registrations were received, and 11 individuals participated. Participants included:

- 2 district foresters from the Authority for Food, Agriculture and Forestry Kempten (TG 4);
- 3 foresters from forest management associations in Füssen, Kaufbeuren, and Oberallgäu (TG 14);
- 1 head of the forest owners' association Kempten (TG 14);
- 5 forest owners from the forest owners' association Holzkirchen (TG 16).

Through collaboration with the forest owners' association, a significant number of forest owners from the Bavarian alpine region were engaged.

Press release and media appearances if present:

To promote the event and ensure broad awareness, news was published on the ifuplan homepage on January 12 (<https://www.ifuplan.de/online-workshop-wertschoepfungskette-wald-einladung-zum-online-workshop-im-rahmen-des-interreg-projekts-forest-ecovalue/>)

and simultaneously on LinkedIn (<https://www.linkedin.com/posts/einladung-projekt-share-7416510785625034754->

[d1ln?utm_source=share&utm_medium=member_desktop&rcm=ACoAAEBelxIB5GaU4A CzCs1UQ0EMak KLSsUo8I](https://www.linkedin.com/posts/einladung-projekt-share-7416510785625034754-d1ln?utm_source=share&utm_medium=member_desktop&rcm=ACoAAEBelxIB5GaU4A CzCs1UQ0EMak KLSsUo8I)).

On February 24, a news article was published on the ifuplan homepage and a LinkedIn post about the workshops was published.

Homepage: [Forest EcoValue: Neue Geschäftsmodelle im Forstbereich](#)

LinkedIn: https://www.linkedin.com/posts/ifuplan_forestecovalue-waldbewirtschaftung-aemkosystemleistungen-activity-7431987798783692800-

[Eren?utm_source=share&utm_medium=member_desktop&rcm=ACoAAEBelxIB5GaU4A_CzCs1UQ0EMAKKLSsUo8I](https://www.eren.com/...?utm_source=share&utm_medium=member_desktop&rcm=ACoAAEBelxIB5GaU4A_CzCs1UQ0EMAKKLSsUo8I)

Workshop 2 – “New value chains for forests 2”

Date: 2 February 2026, 17:00–20:00

Location: Online (Microsoft Teams)

Organiser: ifuplan

The second German capacity building workshop is entitled "New value chains for forests 2" (in German "Neue Wertschöpfungsketten für Wald 2"), which was conducted online on Monday, February 2, 2026. This invitation-only event focused on presenting additional innovative business models and fostering discussions on opportunities, challenges, and solutions for new forestry value chains. A key highlight was the participation of an external expert on burial forests, which enriched the discussions significantly. The workshop was organised by ifuplan and facilitated by Anna Schopf and Franka Beyer. Speakers included Stefan Marzelli, Thomas Dichtl, Andrea Emmer, and an operator of the burial forest Waldruh St. Katharinen.

Objective:

The objectives mirrored those of the first workshop and included:

- Providing comprehensive information about the Forest EcoValue project and its results;
- Presenting selected business models from the Living Lab network and other good practice examples;
- Providing ideas for new forestry value chains;
- Identifying potentials and challenges;
- Formulating recommended actions for policymakers and stakeholders;
- Facilitating dialogue among forest owners, foresters, and local actors;
- A key feature was the contribution of an external expert on burial forests.

Figure 1: PowerPoint-Presentation of the business model "Burial forest" of the German LL

Agenda of the workshop:

- 17:00 – Welcome and introduction
- 17:15 – Presentation of the Project Forest EcoValue
- 17:30 – Presentation of selected business models
- 18:00 – Questions and discussion
- 18:55 – Break
- 19:00 – Collecting results of discussion
- 19:45 – Outlook and project completion
- 20:00 – End of the workshop

Key topics discussed:

The workshop explored a set of innovative forest-based business models, including Reverse Auctions, Burial Forests, integrated ecosystem service value chains, and Tourism Levies, complemented by financing mechanisms such as public subsidy programmes, CO₂ certificate schemes, and drinking water compensation payments.

Participants engaged in structured bilateral exchanges using a Think-Pair-Share approach in Teams to assess the perceived potential of these models, anticipated implementation challenges, and the enabling conditions required for their practical application. Particular attention focused on burial forests, carbon-based financing instruments, tourism-related revenue mechanisms, and public funding schemes, reflecting both their perceived relevance and the level of stakeholder interest.

After these bilateral sessions, participants reconvened for a plenary discussion, where the collective insights and findings were documented on a Miro Board.

Across the discussion, several cross-cutting structural and institutional aspects were raised. Participants reflected on regulatory clarity, administrative feasibility, institutional stability, ownership structures, and coordination mechanisms between sectors and stakeholder groups. The role of municipal financing

instruments, such as tourism-based contributions, was examined, alongside questions of equitable allocation and redistribution of funds. Capacity constraints in education and outreach activities were also discussed, as well as the influence of fragmented private forest ownership and generational characteristics of forest owners on implementation feasibility.

Main outcomes:

The discussions highlighted that diversified business models can contribute to strengthening forest owners' income resilience while supporting multifunctional forest management. However, participants emphasised that successful implementation depends primarily on favourable framework conditions, including regulatory clarity, institutional stability, and feasible governance structures.

A combined approach integrating market-based instruments, locally anchored financing mechanisms, and public support programmes was considered the most robust strategy. Strengthening forest owner associations and intermediary structures emerged as a key enabling factor, particularly in regions characterised by fragmented private ownership.

Overall, the workshop underlined that the long-term viability of innovative forest business models relies not only on their economic design but also on effective coordination, stable policy frameworks, and cooperative implementation structures.

Participants and Stakeholder Groups:

Similar to the first workshop, invitations were extended to 52 organisations from 9 target groups: National Public Authorities (TG 1), Regional Public Authorities (TG 3 and TG 4), Local Public Authorities (TG 5), SMEs

(TG 8), Sectoral agencies (TG 11), Interest groups including NGOs (TG 14), forest owners (TG 16), and Higher education and research organisations (TG 17).

Through established contacts with forest owners' associations (TG 14), extensive reach into the Bavarian alpine region was achieved. A total of 19 registrations were received, and 12 participants attended the workshop. This included:

- 3 district foresters from the Authority for Food, Agriculture and Forestry Kempten (TG 4);
- 1 district forester from the Office for Food, Agriculture and Forestry Weilheim in Upper Bavaria (TG 4);
- 2 foresters from forest management associations in Oberallgäu (TG 14);
- 2 foresters from forest owners' associations Westallgäu and Nordschwaben (TG 14);
- 1 employee from the Nagelfluhkette Nature Park (TG 14);
- 2 forest owners from the forest owners' association Holzkirchen (TG 16).

Additionally, an expert and operator of the burial forest Waldruh St. Katharinen participated, sharing valuable practical experiences.

Press release and media appearances if present:

Promotional efforts for this event included publications on the ifuplan homepage on January 12 (<https://www.ifuplan.de/online-workshop-wertschoepfungskette-wald-einladung-zum-online-workshop-im-rahmen-des-interreg-projekts-forest-ecovalue/>) and on LinkedIn (https://www.linkedin.com/posts/einladung-projekt-share-7416510785625034754-d1ln?utm_source=share&utm_medium=member_desktop&rcm=ACoAAEBelxIB5GaU4A_CzCs1UQ0EMakKLSsUo8I). On February 24, a news article was published on the ifuplan homepage and a LinkedIn post about the workshops was published.

Homepage: [Forest EcoValue: Neue Geschäftsmodelle im Forstbereich](#)

LinkedIn: https://www.linkedin.com/posts/ifuplan_forestecovalue-waldbewirtschaftung-aemkosystemleistungen-activity-7431987798783692800-Eren?utm_source=share&utm_medium=member_desktop&rcm=ACoAAEBelxIB5GaU4A_CzCs1UQ0EMakKLSsUo8I

4.5 Austria

Introduction

As part of the *Forest EcoValue* project, two Capacity Building (CB) Workshops were organised in Austria to promote knowledge exchange and stakeholder engagement around the integration of *Forest Ecosystem Services (FES)* into forest management and policy frameworks.

The events were co-organised by the **University of Graz** and the **Holzcluster Steiermark GmbH (HCS)** within the framework of the Styrian Living Lab.

The **first workshop**, held on **26 June 2025** at the *Holzinnovationszentrum* in Zeltweg, aimed to introduce the *Forest EcoValue* project and the concept of FES, present funding opportunities, and discuss incentives and barriers for forest owners to participate in ecosystem service schemes. Despite active promotion among forest owners' associations, the session was not attended. However, the preparatory and dissemination activities contributed to raising awareness of the initiative at regional level.

The **second workshop**, held on **30 July 2025** at the *Holzcluster Steiermark GmbH* headquarters in Graz, brought together stakeholders from the forestry, research, and policy sectors to discuss the results of the Styrian Living Lab, explore reverse auctions as a potential business model for ecosystem services, and identify next steps for implementing innovative financing mechanisms in forest management.

Overall, these workshops strengthened cooperation between research institutions, public authorities, and private stakeholders in Styria, contributing to the transfer of the *Forest EcoValue* tools and methodologies into the Austrian context.

Workshop 1 – “Secure the Future of Forests and Be Rewarded for It: New Options for Biodiversity and Carbon Stability”

Date: 26 June 2025, 16:00–19:30

Location: Holzinnovationszentrum, Holzinnovationszentrum 1a, 8740 Zeltweg

Organiser: Holzcluster Steiermark GmbH (HCS)

Objective

To introduce the *Forest EcoValue* project and the Styrian Living Lab, highlight the importance of forest ecosystem services, and explore new funding and incentive mechanisms for forest owners, fostering dialogue on how to integrate FES into practical management approaches.

Agenda of the workshop

- 16:30–17:00 | Welcome and Project Introduction
 - *Introduction to the Interreg Alpine Space Project “Forest EcoValue”*
 - *Objectives and benefits of the Living Lab Styria for forest owners*
- 17:00–17:20 | Forest Ecosystem Services (FES) and Funding Opportunities
 - *What services do forests provide for society and the climate?*
 - *Overview of measures, funding logic, and the reverse auction model*
- 10-minute break
- 17:30–18:15 | Motivation and Decision Factors – Group Discussions
 - *Current Status: Which funding programs are being used? What is already being implemented in practice? What challenges exist?*

- *Future Outlook on Ecosystem Services: What motivates forest owners to participate (or not participate)? Personal motivations, obstacles & visions*
- 18:15 | Outlook and Transition to Networking
 - *Initial insights and perspectives for action*
 - *Invitation to network and further participation*
- 18:30 onwards | Open Networking & Closing – *Exchange over drinks and regional specialties*

Key Outcome

Although the event was well prepared and widely promoted (through the local Murtal Forest Owners' Association and online), it was not attended. Nevertheless, the process contributed to increased visibility of the *Forest EcoValue* initiative and served as a preliminary engagement step for subsequent events.

Photos or screenshots

The screenshot shows the registration page for the 'Forest EcoValue – Living Lab Workshop'. At the top, there are navigation links: 'UNSER NETZWERK', 'CLUSTER-LEISTUNGEN', 'AKTUELLES', and 'KONTAKT'. The main banner is yellow with the text 'Forest EcoValue – Living Lab Workshop' and 'Jetzt teilnehmen und Waldzukunft mitgestalten! 26.06.2025 | 16:00 -19:30'. Below the banner, the text reads: 'Im Rahmen des Interreg Alpine Space Projekts **Forest EcoValue** laden wir Sie herzlich zum Living Lab Workshop ein. Gemeinsam mit der **Universität Graz** und dem **Holzcluster Steiermark** möchten wir Ihnen zeigen, wie Sie als Waldbesitzer:in neue Einkommensmöglichkeiten erschließen und gleichzeitig aktiv zum Klimaschutz und zur Biodiversität beitragen können.'

Was erwartet Sie?

- Einblicke in das steirische **Living Lab**, ein Reallabor für innovative, biodiversitätsfördernde Waldbewirtschaftung
- Informationen zu **Fördermöglichkeiten** für Ökosystemleistungen wie Totholzmanagement und Mischwaldentwicklung
- Austausch zu aktuellen Herausforderungen, Förderzugängen und Motivationen
- Vernetzung mit Fachleuten, Projektpartnern und anderen Waldbesitzer:innen bei regionaler Jause

Registration details:

- Ort:** Holzinnovationszentrum, Holzinnovationszentrum 1a, 8740 Zeltweg
- Datum:** 26.06.2025 | 16:00 - 19:30
- Kontakt & Anmeldung:** Kilian Silberschneider, MSc
M: +43 664 167 40 45
E: silberschneider@hiz/holzclustersteiermark.at
- Veranstalter:** Holzcluster Steiermark, hiz

Registration form fields:

- Anmelden**
-
-
-

Online registration webpage

Participants and Stakeholder Groups

Intended audience: regional forest owners, SMEs, forestry associations, and local public authorities (Target Groups 3, 11, 15, 16).

Workshop 2 – “Secure the Future of Forests and Be Rewarded for It: New Options for Biodiversity and Carbon Stability”

Date: 30 July 2025, 14:30–17:00

Location: Holzcluster Steiermark GmbH, Reininghausstraße 13a, 8020 Graz

Organisers: Holzcluster Steiermark GmbH (HCS) and University of Graz

Objective

To present the Forest EcoValue project and its practical application through the Styrian Living Lab, showcase examples from other partner countries, and discuss the feasibility of reverse auctions as an innovative business model for the valuation and remuneration of forest ecosystem services.

Agenda of the workshop

- 14:30–15:00 | Welcome and Technicalities of the Living Lab for the Forest Owners' Association Styria
- 15:00–15:30 | Presentation of the Project and Stakeholder Welcome
 - *Introduction to the Interreg Alpine Space project "Forest EcoValue"*
 - *Ecosystem services of Styrian forests*
 - *Experiences from the Living Lab network*
- 15:30–16:30 | Styrian Living Lab Results
 - *Presentation of outcomes and participants' experiences*
 - *Discussion on motivation, challenges, and contractual conditions*
 - *Future perspectives and next steps*
- 16:30–17:00 | Open Networking and Final Discussion

Key Outcome

The workshop enabled an in-depth discussion among stakeholders from academia, industry, and public administration about the operationalisation of ecosystem service schemes in Austria. Participants expressed strong interest in the reverse auction model and discussed potential governance and contractual frameworks to ensure fair compensation for ecosystem services.

Photos or screenshots

Participants and Stakeholder Groups

Intended audience: regional forest owners, SMEs, forestry associations, and local public authorities (Target Groups 3, 11, 15, 16).

Press release and media appearances if present

<https://www.holzcluster-steiermark.at/news/nachbericht-waldwirtschaft-neu-gedacht-rueckwaertsauktion-als-modell-der-zukunft/>

5. Conclusions

The Capacity Building Workshops implemented under WP3 have played a key role in **ensuring the effective transfer and uptake of the solutions** developed within the Forest EcoValue project. **Between January 2025 and February 2026, a total of 10 Capacity Building Workshops were organised** across the five partner countries (2 per country), **engaging more than 150 stakeholders** from the Alpine Space. Participation ranged from smaller technical sessions (e.g. 7 participants in Italy) to larger national events (e.g. 50 participants in the Italian webinar and 36 participants in the French workshop), ensuring both in-depth validation and broad dissemination. In Germany, the two online workshops involved 23 participants from the Bavarian Alpine region, mainly forest owners and foresters.

The diversity of formats - ranging from local technical meetings and field visits to national webinars – allowed the partnership to address **both operational and governance-related aspects of innovative forest-based business models**. Across the five countries, discussions covered key thematic areas including **carbon and biodiversity credits, reverse auctions, biomass value chains, burial forests, and tourism-related financing mechanisms**.

At the same time, participants highlighted the importance of stable **regulatory frameworks, institutional anchoring, and cooperative governance structures** to ensure long-term implementation and replicability. Particular attention was paid to the role of forest owner associations and intermediary structures in regions characterised by fragmented ownership patterns.

Overall, the CB activities represent a significant step in consolidating the project results, enhancing their visibility beyond the Living Lab territories, and preparing the ground for future policy integration and market uptake across the Alpine Space.

Gefördert durch:

Bundesministerium
für Umwelt, Naturschutz, nukleare Sicherheit
und Verbraucherschutz

aufgrund eines Beschlusses
des Deutschen Bundestages

